

MAIN PURPOSES OF THE TERMINOLOGY IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS AND COMMUNICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The paper is concerned with the most important aspects of the terminology in communication, natural language condition and the special communication condition. The analysis is complemented with cognitive linguistics. In addition, this paper discusses the modern of information extraction method: frame-based terminology. Terminology is specialized in science and many other specialist areas such as politics, culture, technology, chemical technology and the economy. Scholars have defined that the terminology has 3 explanations of the terminology are covered in the paper:

- 1. Terminology is technical language;*
- 2. Terminology is specialized knowledge;*
- 3. Terminology is professional communication; With the right terminology, we can communicate in the "right way". The systematic organization and definition of concepts are called terminology management- which also includes classification.*

Experts use their special language (LSP = language for special purposes) to exchange specialist information, and this special language is distinguished first and foremost by its own special terminology (= specialized vocabulary). The increasing complexity of technical content and of specialist knowledge as a whole, as well as the interlinking and overlapping of specialist subject fields, make ever greater demands on the accuracy of specialist communication. Terminology as a specialist subject and research field has its place here: it helps to make specialist communication quicker and easier and to

ensure its quality by preparing mono- and multilingual specialized vocabularies (= terminologies) and making them available to the widest possible circle of users via the data communications networks.

The theoretical proposals in this field have been mostly practice-based, and focus on the elaboration of glossaries, specialized dictionaries as well as terminological and translation resources. According to Cabré (2000a: 37), "as a subject field with explicit premises, terminology emerges from the need of technicians and scientists to unify the concepts and terms of their subject fields in order to facilitate professional

communication and the transfer of knowledge”.

Cabré (2000) argues in favour of a revised theory of terminology, because it represents one of the lines that provide terminology with the status of being a separate discipline in its own right. To this end, Cabré (2003: 182) starts from two assumptions. Under the first assumption, terminology is “a set of needs, a set of practices to resolve these needs and a unified field of knowledge”. The second assumption is that terminology operates with terminological units which are multi-dimensional and which are simultaneously units of knowledge, units of language and units of communication. The description of these “terminological units” should cover the concept, the term and the situation components. This is what differentiates them from other units of language with the same structural features, i.e. words, and from the units that also express specialized knowledge, i.e. specialized, morphological and phraseological units.

One major tenet of the newly proposed theory is the Principle of the Communicative Nature of Terminology (cf. Cabré 2000: 50). According to this principle, all terminological units “are used for communication, immediately or eventually”. The immediate use of all terminological units refers to the fact that branches of terminology use in only specific way as engineering, medicine and etc.

Under the natural language condition, terms possess a three-fold nature: linguistic, cognitive and social. In this sense, the field of study of terminology is defined in terms of its location within a field of knowledge. This is the only

explanation for the wide range of interpretations of terms that have been offered until now. These interpretations can be summarized as follows (cf. Cabré, 2000: 50): a) for linguistics, terms belong to the lexicon of a grammar, and are specialized according to topical, pragmatic and semantic criteria; b) for special subjects, terms are a means of professional expression and communication and part of a system for representing the structure of knowledge within special areas; c) for translation, interpreting and technical writing, terms are useful and practical units of communication which are evaluated by the criteria of equivalence, adequacy, precision and economy; d) for linguistic planning, terms are lexical units requiring intervention in order to support the existence, usefulness and survival of a language as a means of expression.

The special communication condition which understands special communication as communication marked for topic or domain, produced in professional situations, using a formal register, and being derived from a pre-established structure. Scientific and technical communication realized by special languages differs from the texts used in general communication in three respects: a) semantically, they are concise, precise and not personalized; b) the lexicon has a predominant role, especially the quantitative and qualitative properties of nominalizations and noun phrases; c) formally, texts are highly elaborated and, in some disciplines, elements of other symbolic and semiotic systems are integrated into the text.

The specialization condition is a condition that communication must comply with in order to be considered a special subject

discourse (Cabré, 2000: 52). However, it admits a diversity of interpretations regarding the definition of specialized and different degrees of specialization. If we interpret the adjective “specialized” as referring to discourse dealing with a highly structured scientific or technical subject matter, the notion of specialization is stronger than if we also apply it to specialized activities. In each case, and within each special field, discourse is produced at different levels.

Literature review. In the past, Terminology and Linguistics have mostly ignored each other. In its initial phase, Terminology was interested in asserting its independence from other knowledge areas, and creating a totally autonomous discipline. This goal led terminologists to go to great lengths to emphasize differences between Terminology and Lexicology even to the extent of affirming that terms are not words. In a parallel way, linguistic theory has largely ignored Terminology, probably because specialized language has been and is often regarded as merely a special case of general language. Thus, it was not considered worthy of serious study because anything pertaining to general language was also presumed to be true of specialized language.

Another possible reason for the slow development of Terminology is the lack of interest shown by specialists in other areas of knowledge, such as Linguistics:

The reason, which may explain the continued homogeneity of the established principles, is the lack of interest in terminology by specialists of other branches of science, for example linguistics, psychology, philosophy and history of science and even communication and discourse studies. For many years

terminology saw itself as a simple practice for satisfying specific needs or as a field of knowledge whose signs had nothing to do with the signs of language.

Over the last decade, linguistic theory seems to be in the process of undergoing a cognitive shift (Evans and Green 2006), which has led it to increasingly focus on the conceptual network underlying language. The fact that linguistic form cannot be divorced from meaning has led linguists to begin to explore the interface between syntax and semantics (Faber and Mairal Usón 1999). This trend is also present in the area of Terminology.

Research Methodology. Cognitive-based Terminology theories, though similar in some ways to the Communicative Theory of Terminology, also differ from it. It is not an accident that such theories have arisen largely in the context of Translation. Despite the fact that they also focus on terms in texts and discourse, they make an effort to integrate premises from Cognitive Linguistics and Psychology in their accounts of category structure and concept description. Relevant proposals in this area are Sociocognitive Terminology (Temmerman 1997, 2000, 2006) and Frame-based Terminology (Faber, Márquez Linares, and Vega Expósito 2005; Faber et al. 2006, 2007; Faber and León Araúz 2010; Faber 2011).

Frame-based Terminology: Methodology

Frame-based Terminology focuses on: (1) conceptual organization; (2) the multidimensional nature of terminological units; and (3) the extraction of semantic and syntactic information through the use of multilingual corpora. In this theoretical approach, conceptual networks are based on an underlying domain event, which generates templates for the actions and

processes that take place in the specialized field as well as the entities that participate in them.

Analysis and results. By analyzing concordances, the following information about formation comes to light:

The formation is a process:

1. The process of starting a new substance
2. The process by which something develops into a particular thing or shape
3. Be part of something, to be the thing or one of the things, that is part of substance else, often having a particular use
4. Start to exist, or make a reaction start to exist, especially as the result of a natural process
5. To make something by combining two or more parts
6. To come together in a particular shape or line, or to make something have a particular shape
7. To have strong influence to make a new substance or reaction

This basic information about formation is activated in the creation of the more

specific terms that appear in the corpus, and which are hyponyms of formation. These complex nominal forms are in reality compressed propositions, which have their own syntax.

When specialized knowledge is transferred between language communities, the delimitation of concepts is not always identical in a given pair of languages. In comparative terminology, the process of term identification reveals any discrepancies, as proper designations may not be found in one of the languages. In such cases, the terminologist's role is to describe the gaps and propose designations to fill them. In order for the proposed term to be acceptable and valid, it must be based on sound knowledge of the target language's rules of lexical formation, must be harmoniously integrated into the existing set of terminology, and must be clearly presented as the terminologist's proposal.

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